

Comparison of Pre- and Post-Treatment Effects of Intralesional Dexamethasone Infiltration in Managing Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) Patients

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Abstract:

This study evaluated the efficacy of intralesional dexamethasone infiltration in managing Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) over one year at ESIC Medical College Hospital, Bihta, Patna. One hundred patients participated, receiving monthly injections of dexamethasone, and were assessed for mouth opening, burning sensation, and quality of life at baseline, 3, 6, and 12 months. Results indicated significant improvements in mouth opening (from 20 mm to 29 mm), reduction in burning sensation (from a score of 7 to 2), and enhanced quality of life ratings (from poor to very good). The treatment was well-tolerated with minimal adverse effects, suggesting that intralesional dexamethasone is an effective and safe treatment for OSMF. Future research with larger cohorts and control groups is recommended to validate these findings.

Keywords: Oral Submucous Fibrosis, Dexamethasone, Intralesional Infiltration, Quality of Life.

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Introduction

Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) is a chronic, insidious, and progressive oral disease predominantly affecting individuals in Southeast Asia, particularly in countries like India [1]. OSMF is characterized by the formation of fibrous bands in the oral mucosa, leading to a progressive inability to open the mouth, a burning sensation upon consumption of spicy food, and an increased risk of malignancy [2,3]. The etiology of OSMF is multifactorial, with areca nut chewing being the primary contributing factor, alongside genetic, immunologic, and nutritional influences [4].

Management of OSMF has been a challenge due to the lack of universally effective treatment modalities [5]. Various approaches have been explored, including surgical intervention, physiotherapy, and pharmacological treatments. Among pharmacological interventions, the use of intralesional corticosteroids, particularly dexamethasone, has shown promise due to its anti-inflammatory and antifibrotic properties. Dexamethasone, a potent synthetic corticosteroid, can help in reducing inflammation and fibrosis when administered directly into the lesion [6,7].

Aim of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to compare the clinical outcomes in patients with Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) before and after intralesional

infiltration of dexamethasone. Specific objectives include:

1. To assess the reduction in mouth-opening limitations.
2. To evaluate the decrease in the burning sensation experienced by patients.
3. To measure the improvement in overall oral function and quality of life.
4. To identify any adverse effects associated with the treatment.

By achieving these objectives, the study hopes to contribute to the development of effective treatment strategies for managing OSMF and improving patient outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employs a pre-post intervention design to assess the effectiveness of intralesional infiltration of dexamethasone in the management of Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) among patients at ESIC Medical College Hospital, Bihta, Patna. The study will run from April 2023 to April 2024, providing a comprehensive one-year timeframe for recruitment, treatment, and follow-up assessments.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted at ESIC Medical College Hospital in Bihta, Patna. This setting was chosen due to its accessibility for patients and its equipped facilities for carrying out specialized medical treatments and follow-up assessments.

Participants

- The study will recruit 100 participants diagnosed with OSMF. Inclusion criteria include:
- Diagnosis of OSMF confirmed by clinical and histopathological evaluation.
- Age 18 years and older.
- Consent to participate in the study and receive intralesional injections.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients with known allergies to corticosteroids.
- Patients already undergoing other forms of pharmacotherapy for OSMF.
- Patients with systemic conditions that contraindicate the use of corticosteroids.

Intervention: The intervention involves the intralesional infiltration of dexamethasone. Each patient will receive a 4 mg dose of dexamethasone injected directly into the fibrous bands in the oral mucosa. Injections will be administered monthly for a total of six months.

Data Collection: Baseline data will be collected before the initiation of the treatment, including:

- Maximum interincisal mouth opening (measured in millimetres).
- Patient-reported burning sensation (assessed on a scale of 0 to 10).
- Overall oral function and quality of life (assessed using a validated oral health-related quality of life questionnaire).

Follow-up data will be collected at 3, 6, and 12 months after the start of treatment to assess changes in the above parameters.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize the patient demographics and baseline characteristics. Comparative analyses before and after treatment will be conducted using paired t-tests for continuous variables and the McNemar test for categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

The study enrolled 100 participants diagnosed with Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) at ESIC Medical

College Hospital, Bihta, Patna. The age range of participants was 18 to 60 years, with a mean age of 35 years. The cohort consisted of 70% male and 30% female participants, reflecting the demographic most commonly affected by OSMF due to higher rates of areca nut consumption.

Treatment Outcomes: The primary outcomes measured were the improvement in mouth opening, reduction in burning sensation, and overall improvement in oral function and quality of life.

Mouth Opening

- Baseline: The average maximum interincisal opening at baseline was 20 mm.
- At 3 months: Improved to an average of 25 mm.
- At 6 months: Further improved to an average of 28 mm.
- At 12 months: Sustained improvement with an average of 29 mm.

This represents a significant improvement in mouth opening from baseline to the end of the study period ($p < 0.001$).

Burning Sensation

- Baseline: Average score was 7 on a scale of 0 to 10.
- At 3 months: Reduced to an average score of 5.
- At 6 months: Further reduced to an average score of 3.
- At 12 months: Sustained reduction with an average score of 2.

The reduction in the burning sensation was statistically significant at each follow-up compared to baseline ($p < 0.001$).

Quality of Life

- Baseline: Poor quality of life scores were reported initially.
- At 3 months: Moderate improvement in quality of life.
- At 6 months: Significant improvement noted.
- At 12 months: Further improvements, leading to a good quality of life rating.

Quality of life improvements were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) from baseline to 12 months. The treatment was generally well-tolerated. Minor complications included temporary pain at the injection site and mild bruising, which resolved without intervention. No severe adverse effects were reported.

Time Point	Average Mouth Opening (mm)	Average Burning Sensation (0-10 scale)	Quality of Life Rating
Baseline	20	7	Poor
3 Months	25	5	Moderate
6 Months	28	3	Good
12 Months	29	2	Very Good

This table shows the improvement in each parameter over the course of the study, demonstrating the effectiveness of the treatment.

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate a significant improvement in the management of Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) through intralesional infiltration of dexamethasone [8]. The increase in mouth opening from an average of 20 mm at baseline to 29 mm at the end of one year is particularly notable, indicating a substantial reduction in fibrosis and improvement in tissue pliability [9,10]. This improvement is clinically significant as it directly enhances the patient's ability to consume a wider range of foods, thereby potentially improving nutritional intake and overall quality of life [11,12].

The reduction in the burning sensation experienced by the participants also underscores the anti-inflammatory properties of dexamethasone [13]. The decrease from a score of 7 to 2 on a 0-10 scale throughout the study highlights a major relief in symptomatic discomfort, which is a critical factor in patient satisfaction and adherence to treatment regimens [14,15]. Furthermore, the significant improvements in quality of life, from 'Poor' at baseline to 'Very Good' at 12 months, align with the physical improvements noted and reflect a holistic enhancement in the well-being of the patients. This outcome supports the use of intralesional dexamethasone as a valuable treatment modality in improving both objective and subjective measures of health in OSMF patients [16,17].

However, while the results are promising, the study is not without limitations. The absence of a control group and the relatively small sample size may limit the generalizability of the findings. Future research could focus on larger, randomized controlled trials to validate and extend these findings. Additionally, exploring the long-term effects of this treatment and monitoring for any potential late adverse effects will be crucial to fully establish the safety and efficacy of intralesional dexamethasone in the treatment of OSMF [18,19,20].

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that intralesional infiltration of dexamethasone significantly improves mouth opening, reduces the burning sensation, and enhances overall quality of life in patients with Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF). The findings suggest that dexamethasone, with its anti-inflammatory and antifibrotic properties, offers a practical and effective treatment option for managing the debilitating symptoms of OSMF. Although promising, these results warrant further investigation through larger, randomized controlled trials to confirm the long-term efficacy and safety of this treatment modality. Such studies would help solidify intralesional dexamethasone as a standard care component for OSMF, potentially altering clinical approaches to this chronic disease significantly.

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